

http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT"
3   prefix="og: https://ogp.me/ns#" >
4
5 <head>
6   <meta charset="UTF-8">
7   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, i
8   <link rel="profile" href="https://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
9
10  <title>Marketing Digital Tools</title>
11 <!-- All in One SEO Pack 3.3.5 by Michael Torbert of Semper
12 <meta name="description" content="Agência de Marketing Digi
13 <meta name="keywords" content="Marketing Sites" />
14 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBj98u1EC3V5
15 <script type="application/ld+json" class="aioseop-schema">{
16 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin02.marketingdigitalto
17 <meta property="og:type" content="website" />
18 <meta property="og:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools" />
19 <meta property="og:description" content="Agência de Marketing
20 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin02.marketingdigi
21 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools
22 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin02.marketingdi
23 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary" />
24 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
25 <meta name="twitter:domain" content="https://www.twitter.com/m
26 <meta name="twitter:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools" /
27 <meta name="twitter:description" content="Agência de Marketing
28 <meta name="twitter:image" content="http://plugin02.marketingd
29   <script type="text/javascript" >
30     window.ga=window.ga||function(){(ga.q=ga.q||[]
31     ga('create', 'UA-149501747-1', 'auto');
32     // Plugins
33
34     ga('send', 'pageview');
35   </script>
36   <script async src="https://www.google-analytics.co
37   <!-- All in One SEO Pack -->
38 <link rel="dns-prefetch" href="//s.w.org" />
39 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
40 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
41   <script type="text/javascript">
42     window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl": "https://s.
43     !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("c
44   </script>
45   <style type="text/css">
46   img.wp-smiley,
47   img.emoji {
48     display: inline !important;
49     border: none !important;
50     box-shadow: none !important;
51     height: 1em !important;
52     width: 1em !important;
53     margin: 0 .07em !important;
54     vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
55     background: none !important;
56     padding: 0 !important;
57   }
58 </style>
59   <link rel="stylesheet" id="wp-block-library-css" href="ht
60 <link rel="stylesheet" id="wc-block-style-css" href="http://p
61 <link rel="stylesheet" id="dashicons-css" href="http://plugi
62 <link rel="stylesheet" id="everest-forms-general-css" href="h
63 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-layout-css" href="http
64 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-small-screen-css" href=
65 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-general-css" href="htt
66 <style id="woocommerce-inline-inline-css" type="text/css">
67   .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
68 </style>
69 <link rel="stylesheet" id="font-awesome-css" href="http://pl
70 <link rel="stylesheet" id="zakra-style-css" href="http://plug

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WebPage		All (1)
WebPage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS
ID: http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#webpage		
@type	WebPage	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#webpage	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
inLanguage	pt-PT	
name	marketingdigitaltools.com	
datePublished	2019-02-02T15:11:19+00:00	
dateModified	2020-02-04T12:22:30+00:00	
isPartOf		
@type	WebSite	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#website	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
name	Marketing Digital Tools	
publisher		
@type	Organization	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#organization	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
name	Marketing Digital Tools	
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools	
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/	
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured	
logo		
@type	ImageObject	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Logo-MDT.png	
caption	Logo Marketing Digital Tools	
image		
@type	ImageObject	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Logo-MDT.png	
caption	Logo Marketing Digital Tools	
contactPoint		
@type	ContactPoint	
telephone	+913824934	
contactType	customer support	
about		
@type	Organization	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#organization	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
name	Marketing Digital Tools	
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools	
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/	
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured	
logo		
@type	ImageObject	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Logo-MDT.png	
caption	Logo Marketing Digital Tools	
image		
@type	ImageObject	
@id	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo	
url	http://plugin02.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Logo-MDT.png	
caption	Logo Marketing Digital Tools	
contactPoint		
@type	ContactPoint	
telephone	+913824934	
contactType	customer support	